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Goblin Market: Breaking the Boundaries of Children’s Literature and Exploring Critical Literary Theories

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Abstract:

Christina Rossetti’s *Goblin Market* is an exquisite fairy tale with didactic and moralizing functions at the narrative level. This poem is considered as children’s literature which not only captivates the attention of children but it has many critical implications which is not fully explored. Narrative aporia in this poem leads the reader to ambiguous critical theoretical frameworks where it criticises unregulated capitalism as well as cultural imperialism. These theoretical perspectives of queer space, trauma, market economy and sexual encounter drive the poem towards adult readers. As a moral fable, this poem shows the ideal relationship of two sisters namely Laura and Lizzie but on the figurative level, this poem shows the homoerotic relationship of sisterhood. consumption of Goblin's fruits examines how exotic commodity display can tempt the consumers. The description of Goblins pointed out Freud's theory of uncanny and racial iconography in the society. Women's agency in the poem gives a feminist perspective as well which not only questions the gender role but takes a nonconformist stand. This paper aims to explore The *Goblin Market*’s critical, analytical and theoretical prospects which break the boundaries of Children’s literature and give more space to new literary and theoretical approaches.

Keywords: Goblin Market, Christina Rossetti, Queer Theory, Trauma Theory, Children's Literature.

Introduction

Some historians of children's literature pointed out in the middle of the nineteenth century that didacticism was introduced into this genre of children's literature where it functions to shape children with moral and ethical values. *Goblin Market* (1862) fit into the same tradition of children's literature which outwardly gives moral lesson to children, but it has many theoretical implications. At the narrative level it narrates the story of two maiden girls, namely, Lizzie and Laura who had to encounter with Goblins who were portrayed as non-human, animal-like figures. Penniless Laura uses a golden lock from her hair as a mode of transaction to get those tempting fruits, symbolizing the dangers of feminine consumerism by embracing the thing that is being devoured. This market analysis inspires Lizzie to utilize money instead, finding value in a silver penny to exchange for protection of her own body and the restoration of Laura's health. In this market, only sisterhood seems to have any staying power, albeit it is frustratingly still unclear why. Twentieth century critics did not give much attention to the significance of kinship in the poem which contributed to economic discourse and the importance of money and trade in saving Laura and Lizzie.

Most of the critics of the nineteenth century used to consider this poem as an allegory due to its didactic function and moralizing effect. In 1863, one year after of *Goblin Market's* publication, Caroline Norton wrote for Macmillan's Magazine where he tried to highlight the duality of *Goblin Market*.

Is it a fable-or a mere fairy story-or an allegory against the pleasures of sinful love or what is it? Let us not too rigorously inquire, but accept it in all its quaint and pleasant mystery, and quick and musical rhythm-a ballad which children will con with delight. And which riper minds may ponder over (Norton 250).

Narrative aporia in the text leads towards ambiguity, but it also creates possibilities of interpretations. Some critics found traces of colonialism in this poem; some critics examines this text through the lens of feminism and capitalism where Lizzie becomes a non-conformist voice against the patriarchal and the male dominated market. This paper explored the areas of critical theoretical interpretations of *Goblin Market* which is still not fully explored.

It's vital to keep in mind that while children to whom Laura narrates her narrative are the internal audience of *Goblin Market*, but the poem's focused audience was adults rather than children. Publisher Alexander Macmillan in October 1861 read aloud Christina Rossetti's this masterpiece to a Cambridge working men's organization. Macmillan wrote a letter to Christiana Rossetti's brother Dante Gabriel Rossetti about workers' response where he stated, "They seemed at first to wonder whether I was making fun of them," he also said "By degrees they got stated, "as still as death, and when I finished there was a tremendous burst of applause" (Macmillan 95). The men's thought that Macmillan was mocking them indicates that their initial impression of the poem's nursery rhyme meters and skipping rhymes was that they were being patronized by a fairy tale aimed at youngsters. Their ensuing quietness and appreciation showed those workers' acceptance of *Goblin Market's* topic content and suitability for adult readers. Rossetti undoubtedly purposefully employed the structure or form of a fairy tale which is apposite for its oral reading to communicate an underling message and the narrative to the wider group of adults.

Goblin Market was penned in 1859, during Rossetti's tenure as a lay sister at Highgate Penitentiary, an institution dedicated to the reformation of women who had strayed from societal norms, as detailed in Jan Marsh's study. Marsh claims that although this poem was probably not "explicitly written for the girls or Sisters at Highgate," it is quite likely to have been influenced by Rossetti's own life experiences in this context (Marsh, "Christina Rossetti's vocation," 244–45).

Rossetti's creative genius become crystal like clear to the critics when she had used symbols which works as a hiding mechanism to hide its adult comment. There is a moral lesson which came out with some biblical connotations where he takes the concept of temptation from bible and implied that concept in her own poetry. The fruit was symbolized as temptation and its presentation was tempting as well. Rossetti wrote –

Our grapes fresh from the vine,
Pomegranates full and fine,
Dates and sharp bullaces,
Rare pears and greengages,
Damsons and bilberries,
Taste them and try:
(Rossetti, *Goblin Market* ,20-25)

The tone in which goblins were trying to gather the attention of the maidens has some sexual connotations. This created the scope for the critics to introspect this literary text more than a children's literature and places this text in the sphere of adults.

Consumption becomes one of the prominent themes of this text. Goblin men are the merchants in Rossetti's poem and maidens are their customers. When Lizzie and Laura leave their house and enter the patriarchal market in Rossetti's creative space, they traverse a fictitious but deeply held line dividing not only serious and meaningful poetry from children's literature but also explores its female characters beyond of capitalist production and gender roles. The fact that women were considered signs of luxury in eighteenth- and nineteenth-century affluent culture, representing in their personas the ability of the men in their lives, or lovers to consume, is likely the root of the strong links between women and consumerism. Where this position of authority was despised, female consumerism was condemned; where it was praised, women were anticipated to purchase and show the trinkets that also served as symbols of affluence and leisure. Women exhibited the showy consumerism that gave males social status in the rococo society of eighteenthcentury France and, afterward, in the middleclass world in nineteenth century England.

As a result, "Goblin Market" is a provocative poem that refutes several linked distinctions based on the falsehood that moral women differ from men who were dominating the economic sphere, a falsehood that most of the writings of nineteenth century and thought as very normal phenomena. In order to preserve gendered disparities, the narrative of those maiden girls depicted female experience in the political, economic sphere of mid-Victorian England. This experience is frequently obscured and eliminated from creative and analytical explanations of that economy's activities. The economics of marriage and sex in Rossetti's work is essentially one of consumption. In some of the most critical analyses of capitalist relations, concepts of gender difference paradoxically negate women's unique experiences with consuming, according to a cursory glance at some other writings on consumption.

Literary critics started paying closer attention to the numerous economies that *Goblin Market* staged and exposed in the 1990s, including the political, sexual, and intertextual ones. Some critics have emphasized the complex ways in which the poem deals with sexuality and gender representing Victorian sensibility, but literary critic like Terrence Holt, who claims that modern critics discuss “the goblins... and the issues of sexuality and gender they seem to represent” without regard for “the market.” (Holt 51). Readers have largely maintained to perceive the plot as more or less coherent, despite attempts to locate the poem's numerous transactions into broader frameworks of Victorian culture, politics, and market events.

Rossetti's *Goblin Market* (1862), in contrast, is more subtly taciturn in conveying its queer agenda, with the gay identities of its individuals acting more as a supporting theme than as the text's primary focus. However, there are verified tales that chronicle the presence of female-female affect significantly earlier in history than the time when Rossetti wrote the poem. The term lesbian was not in widely used while Rossetti wrote *Goblin Market*, similar to how the term gay was not in common usage in Tennyson's time.

While she had to maintain secrecy about her unconventional aspirations and often had to disavow any knowledge of “sexual activity between women,” similar to how Tennyson and Rossetti concealed their unconventional desires within their poetry, it's worth noting that the term “sapphism” used to describe female-female relationships in Rossetti's era implies a different form of sexuality compared to contemporary female-female unions. Nevertheless, the emotional desire indicated by both “sapphism” and “lesbianism” remains a shared experience. Both words view female-female sex as transgressive and the joy that results from pursuing one's own sexual impulses as being of utmost significance to politically imposed social conventions. As a result, they both work to dismantle those conventions. In addition, Bernadette J. Brooten cites a number

of terminologies, such as ‘hetairistria’, that were used in ancient Greek society to describe women who engaged in sexual activity with other women before the term lesbian was coined, concluding that this “demonstrates the existence of a cultural category of homoerotic women” (Bernadette 337).

While reading the text, readers will come across these lines:

She cried “Laura,” up the garden,
“Did you miss me
Come and kiss me,
Never mind my bruises,
Hug me, kiss me, suck my juices
Squeezed from goblin fruits for you,
Goblin pulp and goblin dew.
Eat me, drink me, love me;
Laura, make much of me:
For your sake I have braved the glen
And had to do with goblin merchant men.” (464-474).

New-critical reading of these lines draw its reader's attention towards more unexplored domain of sexuality where Laura was asking her sister Lizzie to hug her, kiss her and suck all the juices from her body. Some critics claim that these lines represent oneness of two sisters, but their claim could not hide Laura and Lizzie's erotic and queer identity. There is a quest for exploring one's sexuality which was portrayed with Laura's character who at first went to those goblins

after hearing their tempting cries to explore her own sexuality. Lizzie on the other hand was a welldeveloped and mature character who not just denied to accept fruits from goblins but also enter into male dominated marketpace by giving them her silver penny.

So, there is clear historical precedent for queer affect, but hegemonic ideologies like heteronormativity and homonormativity try to hide these queer histories. This once again demonstrates how important it is to look into both the major historical cultural artifacts of humanity and the present in order to continue to highlight the presence of such historical queer identities.

In the context of imperial capitalism's economics, the poem explores the complex connection that exists among women and the Eastern beauty they embraced. This chapter examines how a consciousness of the manners of how capital mobilized to encourage female involvement with the marketpace, even it tries to enshrine women among the imperialistic representation of market through its development of female as customers of oriental goods, enhances the reception of Rossetti's poem. The colonial exhibitionary complex of opulent stores, which aimed to decontextualize oriental products and forbid women from identifying with the forces of oppressed labour by which these items were produced, served as the vehicle for this provocation.

Within this imperial-commercial scheme, women held a conflicting position, which capitalism ventured to manage by creating female as the connoisseurs rather than the devoured. But rather than turning away from these economies' symbolic principles, women shoppers may undermine this situation and upset capitalism by pursuing other kinds of desire within them. Similar to a fetish, the commodity creates a paradox that makes it possible for different forms of desire that endanger the idea that empire will continue to exist.

The scholastic repertoire of “Goblin Market,” Rossetti’s most well-known poem, is exceptionally mercantile. The repeated shout of the “merchant men” that punctuates the text, “Come buy, come buy,” is unique in nineteenth-century English poetry. As with its rhymes and goblins, most of the discourses regarding “Goblin Market” takes its tale of purchasing and selling as the figurative garb for a story about religious enticement, decline of moral values, and redemption. What happens, though, if we interpret the figure as a subject instead—specifically, the relationship between women and the markets shown in children’s stories?

Rossetti’s poem presents a provocative notion that Laura and fellow fallen women could potentially undergo complete redemption. During the Victorian era, prevailing societal beliefs often condemned women who had strayed from purity to a state of irreparable alienation, relegating them to roles like servants or emigrants. However, in the poem, Laura’s redemption is informed by both spiritual salvation and a more commercial interpretation of redemption. It’s as though her lost attributes, her hair and innocence, were not irretrievably gone, but rather akin to commodities that could have been pawned, and Lizzie possesses the power to fully restore them. This transaction introduces the notion that a woman’s sexual purity, decried in the poem as a marketable commodity, might also be reclaimed through an alternative form of market exchange, one extending beyond mere compensation but remaining advantageous in its own unique manner.

Within *Goblin Market*, the central inquiry transcends mere participation or avoidance of the market by women; it delves into the intricate realm of women’s desires devoid of associated costs. Rossetti doesn’t delineate a strict dichotomy between the marketplace and the domestic sphere. Instead, the poem grapples with the intricate entwinement of women within capitalist structures and how capitalism exerts a profound influence on the desires of women and their proclivity to engage with the imperial exhibitionary context of the marketplace. This

manifestation of affirmative desire, wherein women partake in consumption without becoming commodities themselves and engage in observation without engaging in transactions, finds its vivid representation through the actions of Laura and Lizzie in *Goblin Market*. They acquire the skill of observing and obtaining what they desire amid the mesmerizing allure of exotic commodities, all the while eluding the engulfing nature of consumption.

Critics uncover an unusual yet intriguing examination by a seemingly withdrawn Victorian woman poet who explores the intricacies of a commercialized, racially divided market in what is possibly the most celebrated poem about a shopping trip in the history of English literature. The poem "Goblin Market" reveals its radical essence through its support of women's desires in the backdrop of Britain's growing imperial consumer culture.

Decoding Christina Rossetti's *Goblin Market* only as an Adult sexual fantasy would be not appropriate as this poem has much more significance as this poem deals with colonial modernity due to its micronarratives. Undoubtedly it could be said that this poem delves into the exploration of masochism, homoeroticism, rape, or incest which is deeply intertwined with human passions. On a greater level, the language of this poem is similar to the writings of Emily Dickinson, one of the other Victorian poets who formed a distinct category of poetry where lyrics speak directly to and about the psyche, expressing and querying feelings that are deliberately abstracted from any references to, or analysis of the social causes of psychological states. Rossetti's poem plays with the duality of present and absent meanings which leads towards a vacuum of concrete meaning. Imperialism as a subject matter and as a motif is as much relevant as the Study of the poem from the perspective of Feminism and Marxism. Through the lances of poststructuralism, this poem gains much more relevance as structuralism totally believes in the oppositional meaning-making process of literary texts and in this poem itself Rossetti explores

many different dimension critical theoretical perspectives that lead towards micronarratives and different dimensions of meanings. Thus this poem breaks the boundaries of children's literature and explores many various critical theoretical aspects and creates a new window of familiarization with theoretical traditions.

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